

Hybrid-Driven Deep Learning Networks for Communication

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Abstract

This article introduces the Imp-CsiNet, a deep neural network used to solve excessive CSI feedback overhead. The network uses a codec architecture and introduces an attention mechanism in the encoder to increase the network's attention to important local features of CSI data. Partly combined with the idea of Inception architecture, the convolution kernel of different receptive fields can improve the network's ability to parse compressed codebooks. Experiments show that Imp-CsiNet can surpass the existing superior network in reconstruction performance.

Introduction

The massive MIMO is one of the core technologies of 5G mobile communication. As shown in Fig. 1, wireless communication system can achieve the performance gain by precoding the channel state information (CSI) transmitted from the user equipment to the base station. However, the large number of antennas in a massive MIMO system will cause excessive CSI feedback overhead. Therefore, reducing the CSI feedback overhead has become an urgent problem to be solved.

Fig. 1 CSI feedback mechanism

Network

In order to solve the problem of CSI feedback overhead, we adopt a codec architecture and replace the encoder and decoder with a deep network. In the encoder part, as shown in Fig. 2, we first implement the preliminary feature extraction of the input data through the convolution layer, then apply the attention mechanism to the CSI data in the channel domain and spatial domain in parallel through the CSAR module, and then pass the convolution layer Integration, and then through the compression of the fully connected layer to get a compressed codebook. In the decoder part, as shown in Fig. 3, we first perform feature analysis on the compressed codebook, and then perform further feature extraction on the compressed codebook through the two-layer Inception-Refine network, and finally obtain the reconstructed CSI data through the convolutional layer. The overall architecture of Imp-CsiNet is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 2 Imp-CsiNet Encoder

Fig. 3 Imp-CsiNet Decoder

Fig. 4 Imp-CsiNet network structure

Experiments

We chose COST 2100 to generate the data set needed for the experiment. The specific generated data contains two scenarios, namely indoor 5.3GHz channel data and outdoor 300MHz channel data. Each scenario generates 10,000 training sets, 30,000 verification sets, and 20,000 tests. set. The training of the network is completed on NVIDIA 1080ti. The epochs, learning rate, and batch size are set as 1000, 0.001, and 200, respectively.

The corresponding experimental results are shown in Table I. Imp-CsiNet's reconstruction quality at each compression ratio exceeds the algorithm based on compressed sensing, while leading the original CsiNet.

TABLE I
NMSE in dB and COSINE SIMILARITY

Compression Rate	Algorithm	5.3GHz Indoor		300MHz Outdoor	
		NMSE	ρ	NMSE	ρ
1/4	LASSO	-7.59	0.91	-5.08	0.82
	BM3D-AMP	-4.33	0.80	-1.33	0.52
	TVAL3	-14.87	0.97	-6.90	0.88
	CsiNet	-17.36	0.99	-8.75	0.91
	Imp-CsiNet	-27.10	0.99	-12.85	0.95
1/16	LASSO	-2.72	0.70	-1.01	0.46
	BM3D-AMP	0.26	0.16	0.55	0.11
	TVAL3	-2.61	0.66	-0.43	0.45
	CsiNet	-8.65	0.93	-4.51	0.79
	Imp-CsiNet	-13.92	0.98	-6.04	0.85
1/32	LASSO	-1.03	0.48	-0.24	0.27
	BM3D-AMP	24.72	0.04	22.66	0.04
	TVAL3	-0.27	0.33	0.46	0.28
	CsiNet	-6.24	0.89	-2.81	0.67
	Imp-CsiNet	-9.57	0.94	-3.73	0.74
1/64	LASSO	-0.14	0.22	-0.06	0.12
	BM3D-AMP	24.93	0.04	25.45	0.03
	TVAL3	0.63	0.11	0.76	0.19
	CsiNet	-5.84	0.87	-1.93	0.59
	Imp-CsiNet	-7.62	0.91	-2.53	0.65

Conclusion

This paper introduces the neural network used to solve the excessive CSI feedback overhead, and the network's reconstruction performance far exceeds the method based on compressed sensing, and at the same time exceeds the original CsiNet.

References

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